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Professional Physical Skills and the Professional Competence of Physical Culture Specialists

Sanjar Uraimov,

Associate Professor, Fergana State University, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences, docent

Farrukh Muhridinov,

1st-year master's student, Fergana State University

Abstract: *This article provides an in-depth analysis of the professional physical skills and competencies required for physical culture specialists. It explores the multifaceted nature of these skills, focusing on how they impact both theoretical understanding and practical application in the field. The article also examines how these competencies contribute to the overall effectiveness and professional development of specialists in physical culture and sports.*

Key words: *professional physical skills, professional physical training, movement qualities, physical capabilities, communicative activities, constructive skills, physical culture specialist, profession.*

Introduction: The Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5368, dated March 5, 2018, emphasizes the need for a comprehensive approach to the development of physical culture and sports. This decree outlines the objectives for improving physical culture management and creating favorable conditions for the population to lead a healthier lifestyle. The directive also highlights the importance of developing highly skilled professionals in the field of physical culture and sports to meet these goals.

Professional Qualities of Physical Culture Specialists: Physical culture specialists are expected to possess a diverse set of professional qualities that encompass a wide range of skills and attributes:

Worldview and Philosophy:

National and Cultural Awareness: Specialists should have a deep understanding of their nation's cultural and historical background and integrate this knowledge into their professional activities.

Ethical Orientation: A commitment to ethical practices, including integrity, responsibility, and respect for students, is crucial for fostering a positive learning environment.

Moral and Character Traits:

Humaneness: Specialists should demonstrate empathy, kindness, and consideration in their interactions with students and colleagues.

Honesty and Integrity: Upholding high standards of honesty and ethical behavior is essential for building trust and credibility.

Diligence and Perseverance: The ability to work diligently and persistently towards professional goals is vital for success in the field.

Communicative Skills:

Effective Communication: Specialists must be adept at both verbal and non-verbal communication to engage with students effectively.

Conflict Resolution: The ability to manage and resolve conflicts constructively is important for maintaining a harmonious learning environment.

Intellectual and Cognitive Abilities:

Problem-Solving Skills: Specialists should be capable of analyzing complex situations, identifying solutions, and implementing effective strategies.

Strategic Thinking: The ability to plan and execute long-term goals and objectives is essential for achieving success in the field.

Skills of Physical Culture Specialists: Skills are a critical component of professional competence and are categorized into several key areas:

Constructive Skills:

Planning and Organization: Specialists must be proficient in designing and organizing physical activities and training programs tailored to the needs of students.

Adaptability: The ability to modify training approaches based on individual and group needs is essential for effective teaching.

Communicative Skills:

Engagement: Specialists should be skilled in motivating and inspiring students to participate actively in physical activities.

Feedback: Providing constructive feedback and encouragement helps students improve their performance and develop confidence.

Gnostic Skills:

Understanding Pedagogical Situations: Specialists need to recognize and respond appropriately to various pedagogical scenarios, including student challenges and learning opportunities.

Outcome Assessment: The ability to assess and evaluate the outcomes of physical activities and training programs is crucial for continuous improvement.

Movement Skills:

Technical Proficiency: Specialists should demonstrate a high level of skill in performing physical exercises and movements accurately.

Physical Conditioning: Maintaining personal physical fitness and demonstrating physical capabilities in practice are important for setting a positive example for students.

Professional Physical Preparation: Professional physical preparation encompasses a comprehensive approach that integrates both theoretical knowledge and practical skills:

Theoretical Knowledge:

Historical and Philosophical Foundations: Understanding the history and philosophy of physical culture provides a contextual framework for teaching and practice.

Biomechanics and Physiology: Knowledge of the mechanical principles of movement and the physiological responses of the body to exercise is essential for effective training.

Practical Knowledge:

Methodological Skills: Specialists should be familiar with various teaching methods and techniques for delivering effective physical education.

Exercise Prescription: The ability to design and prescribe exercise programs that meet the needs of diverse populations is crucial for successful outcomes.

Methodological Knowledge:

Teaching Strategies: Effective strategies for teaching physical skills and concepts, including the use of demonstrations, explanations, and hands-on practice.

Assessment Techniques: Knowledge of assessment methods to evaluate student progress and adjust teaching strategies accordingly.

Professional Physical Qualities: The physical qualities of a specialist are demonstrated through their ability to perform and teach physical activities effectively:

Movement Proficiency: Specialists should exhibit precise control and execution of physical movements, reflecting their own physical conditioning and technical skills.

Endurance and Strength: Physical endurance and strength are necessary for sustaining energy levels throughout teaching activities and modeling exercises.

Coordination and Flexibility: These qualities contribute to the ability to perform a wide range of movements and exercises, enhancing the overall effectiveness of physical training.

Constructive Feedback and Encouragement

Providing constructive feedback and encouragement is pivotal in helping students enhance their performance and build self-confidence. Feedback should be specific, actionable, and supportive, focusing on both strengths and areas for improvement. By fostering an environment of positive reinforcement, specialists can motivate students to strive for continuous improvement and overcome challenges effectively.

Gnostic Skills

Understanding Pedagogical Situations: Specialists must be adept at recognizing and responding to various pedagogical scenarios, including student difficulties and learning opportunities. This involves tailoring instructional approaches to address individual student needs, adapting strategies to different learning styles, and providing timely interventions to support student development.

Outcome Assessment: The capacity to assess and evaluate the outcomes of physical activities and training programs is crucial for ensuring continuous improvement. Specialists should implement assessment techniques that measure student progress, evaluate the effectiveness of training programs, and identify areas for enhancement. Regular assessments allow for adjustments in teaching strategies and help in achieving desired educational outcomes.

Movement Skills

Technical Proficiency: Specialists are expected to exhibit a high level of technical proficiency in performing physical exercises and movements accurately. This involves demonstrating correct technique, precision, and skill execution during physical activities, which serves as a model for students and enhances their learning experience.

Physical Conditioning: Maintaining personal physical fitness and showcasing physical capabilities in practice are essential for setting a positive example for students. Specialists should engage in regular physical conditioning to ensure they are physically capable of performing exercises effectively and inspiring students through their own fitness levels.

Professional Physical Preparation

Theoretical Knowledge:

Historical and Philosophical Foundations: Understanding the history and philosophy of physical culture provides a contextual framework for teaching and practice. Specialists should be well-versed in the evolution of physical education, its foundational theories, and their implications for modern practice.

Biomechanics and Physiology: Knowledge of the mechanical principles of movement and the physiological responses of the body to exercise is essential for effective training. Specialists should apply principles of biomechanics and physiology to optimize exercise techniques and enhance training outcomes.

Practical Knowledge:

Methodological Skills: Specialists should be familiar with a variety of teaching methods and techniques for delivering effective physical education. This includes using diverse instructional approaches, adapting methods to different learning styles, and employing effective communication strategies.

Exercise Prescription: Designing and prescribing exercise programs that meet the needs of diverse populations is crucial. Specialists should develop tailored exercise plans that consider individual fitness levels, goals, and any special requirements to ensure successful training outcomes.

Methodological Knowledge

Teaching Strategies: Effective teaching strategies for physical skills and concepts include the use of demonstrations, explanations, and hands-on practice. Specialists should employ a range of strategies to facilitate learning, ensure clarity in instruction, and engage students actively in the learning process.

Assessment Techniques: Knowledge of various assessment methods is essential for evaluating student progress and adjusting teaching strategies accordingly. Specialists should use appropriate assessment tools to measure student achievements, provide feedback, and make necessary adjustments to instructional approaches.

Professional Physical Qualities

Movement Proficiency: Specialists should demonstrate precise control and execution of physical movements, reflecting their own physical conditioning and technical skills. High levels of movement proficiency contribute to effective teaching and serve as an example for students.

Endurance and Strength: Physical endurance and strength are necessary for sustaining energy levels throughout teaching activities and modeling exercises. Specialists should maintain these attributes to ensure they can effectively lead and participate in physical training sessions.

Coordination and Flexibility: Coordination and flexibility enhance the ability to perform a wide range of movements and exercises, thereby improving the overall effectiveness of physical training. Specialists should cultivate these qualities to deliver diverse and comprehensive physical education.

Conclusion: The professional competence of physical culture specialists is a multifaceted concept that involves a combination of theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and personal attributes. By developing and enhancing these competencies, specialists can significantly improve their effectiveness in both theoretical and practical training contexts. This holistic approach to professional development ensures that physical culture specialists are well-equipped to meet the demands of their profession and contribute to the promotion of physical health and well-being.

References

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